

Fuel Cell Power Pack with Integrated Metal Hydride Hydrogen Storage for Powering Electric Forklift

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1 Introduction

Fuel cells are gaining more attention in material handling industry as they provide numerous benefits for warehouses, airports, seaports, etc. European Commission (EC) recognized the importance of the fuel cell and hydrogen technology and their inevitable role in reducing greenhouse gas emission by further encouraging hydrogen fuel cells in heavy-duty vehicles in their hydrogen strategy for a climate-neutral Europe [1]. Fuel cell-powered forklifts possess several advantages over the battery-powered ones: operation time up to 8 h on a single tank of hydrogen, constant power throughout an entire shift, lower refueling time, stable operation, etc. Also, fuel cell-powered forklifts allow maximization of warehouse floor as no additional power modules are needed per forklift. For battery-powered forklifts, at least, two to three battery packs are needed—one deployed in the forklift, one on charging, and one on cooling. As each battery has a volume of $\sim 1 \text{ m}^3$ —switching to fuel cell-powered modules allows maximizing warehouse space utilization and reducing operational costs. Due to these factors, fuel cell hydrogen-fueled forklifts became a promising early market niche application. At the moment, more than 20,000 fuel cell-powered forklift are been deployed in warehouses, stores, and other manufacturing facilities in the United States, as compared to only 500 in Europe and 100 in Japan [2, 3].

As a rule, fuel cell-powered forklifts utilize a hybrid power train when fuel cell delivers average power, and the peak power is provided by batteries or supercapacitors. The development of a hybrid power train with a 16 kW polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cell system, ultracapacitor modules, and lead-acid battery was reported in [4]. Reference [5] reports about the implementation of the hybrid power train which supplied the required 50 kW peak power in a typical forklift work cycle. Five prototypes fuel cell-powered forklifts were built, tested in laboratory, and delivered to Taiwanese supermarket warehouse. Each hybrid-drive system included 2.7 kW proton exchange membrane fuel cell stack, lithium battery pack, and supercapacitors. The components of the drive system could supply 7 kW of electric power. In Ref. [6], a game theory model was developed to

assess the potential of fuel cell and battery-powered forklifts for reducing greenhouse gas emissions in the Ontario province, Canada. Their analysis showed that battery-powered forklifts are more cost-effective compared to fuel cell-powered ones but only when lower levels of discounted power are available. On other hand with increased social cost of carbon (SCC) and discounted power available—fuel cell-powered forklifts become more cost-effective. Also, it was found that fuel cell-powered forklifts have lower operational and maintenance costs over the battery-powered, and that both technologies are highly effective in reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Economic comparison study between fuel cell and battery-powered forklift was done in Ref. [7] for different forklift power plants. It was found out that fuel cell forklifts are more expensive to purchase and to operate for the facility with fleet of 50 forklifts. As this study is based on relatively old data from 2010 and taking into account that fuel cell power module and refueling station purchase prices are significantly lower than at the time when this study was accomplished—new study preferably with the higher number of deployed forklifts (>100) and considering different refilling station technologies (i.e., metal hydride) urgently must be done. Performance simulation of hybrid PEM fuel cell/battery-powered forklifts was done in Ref. [8]. Study was done for different combinations of lead-acid battery capacity and fuel cell stack sizes with conjunction of two different control strategies to investigate hydrogen consumption and battery state-of-charge. Comparison was done for two different load cycles, and it was found that combination of 110 cells stacked with two 55 Ah batteries provides most economical combination in terms of hydrogen consumption. A similar study has been recently performed [9] for different load cycles (VDI60) and working conditions. It was found out that optimal battery capacity for a 3-ton electric forklift is 10 Ah with fuel cell stack power of 11 kW. So far, almost, all demonstrated FC-powered utility vehicles used compressed H₂ stored in composite gas cylinders at pressures up to 350 bar. This solution is associated with too big volume of the onboard hydrogen storage component (storage density 0.02 kg H₂/L) and its insufficient weight to provide vehicle stability during operation. To mitigate the latter problem, an additional ballast is required for proper vehicle counterbalancing. In addition, the high H₂ storage pressure poses safety concerns and requires expensive refueling infrastructure. The problems can be solved using metal hydrides (MH) for the onboard hydrogen storage [3–5, 10]. HySA Systems in 2012 developed a metal hydride hydrogen storage extension tank which was successfully integrated in a commercial GenDrive 1600-80CEA fuel cell power module (Plug Power Inc.) and tested onboard 3-ton electric forklift from STILL [11]. Since 2015 developed prototype operates at Impala Platinum in Springs, and so far, only, problems were related to Li-ion battery pack. Test results of this prototype were presented in Ref. [12]. Based on the tests at the Impala Refinery, it was found that forklift can operate ~3 h for heavy-duty operation (VDI60 cycles) and ~7 h for light duty operation. Here, we present a developed power fuel cell pack with MH hydrogen storage which was developed by Hydrogen South Africa Systems [13] and integrated by Hot Platinum (Pty) Ltd, South Africa. Forklift was successfully tested according to “Verein Deutscher Ingenieure” (VDI60) drive cycle protocol to identify optimization ways for improvement of operational stability at high loads, decreasing hydrogen consumption, and balance-of-plant (BoP) power demands.

2 Experimental

2.1 Fuel Cell Power Module

Liquid-cooled PEM fuel cell stack from Ballard with 75 cells and 15 kW power output was integrated into power pack module. Liquid cooled/heated MH tank developed by HySA Systems was used for efficient hydrogen storage and as a ballast to achieve fully rated forklift lifting capacity. Developed novel MH tank allowed decreasing of hydrogen pressure on the high-pressure side of hydrogen subsystem from 13.5 to 3.4 bar and reducing refueling pressure to 100 bar [11].

Power pack specifications are depicted in Table 1.

Table 1 Power pack specifications

Vehicle	STILL RX60-30L
Bus voltage	80 VDC
Output power	~15 kW average, 30 kW peak
Dimensions	840 mm (W) × 1010 mm (D) × 777 mm (H)
Weight	1800, ..., 1900 kg
Stack	14.5 kW closed cathode PEMFC stack (Ballard)
H ₂ storage	Integrated MH storage unit, 20 Nm ³
Battery bank	Deep cycle lead-acid, 8, ..., 10 kWh

Power module concept design is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Power module concept design

2.2 “Zero” Prototype—Bench-Top Version

To optimize balance-of-plant special fuel cell testbed was developed and tested, Fig. 2. In order to reduce system costs, we used standard components mainly from automotive industry such as valves, coolant pumps, heat exchangers, different flow meters, and filters. Individual cell voltage was monitored by specially developed CVM system, and to simulate different operating conditions, load bank resistors have been used.

Fig. 2 “Zero” prototype—bench-top version

2.3 Optimal BoP Design and Electrical Layout

Balance-of-plant design is presented in Fig. 3. The BoP is designed around liquid-cooled closed cathode Ballard 9SSL/75 cell FC stack (14.4 kW rated power; 48.2 V DC at 300 A).

Optimal electrical layout (which was reached after several iterations) is presented in Fig. 4. In order to compensate for the peak power draw of the load, an ultracapacitor (Maxwell, 97.2 V; 83 F) was introduced in parallel with the lead-acid battery pack. Main malfunctions identified during off-boards test of the commercial power module (from Plug Power Inc.) under real environmental conditions were mainly related to Li-ion batteries. To mitigate problems that occurred with the commercial fuel cell-powered module, we decided to integrate a lead-acid battery bank (6 × 12 V/100 Ah deep cycle SLA). Auxiliaries were connected directly to 24 and 48 V branches of the battery bank thus avoiding additional DC-to-DC converters.

3 Results

3.1 Off-Board Tests

Off-board tests were performed by connecting bench-top version with the resistive load bank to emulate a drive cycle based on the data provided from the VDI60 test with a

Fig. 5 Off-board test results of power module

3.2 Onboard Tests

Forklift was tested according to VDI60 standard protocol [14]. VDI60 testing protocol consists of 45 cycles in 60 min. Each cycle consists of forklift at starting position “1” holding 70% of rated load capacity (our test were performed with 100% rated load capacity of 3 ton), forward driving to position “2” (1.5 m distance) and lifting load up to 2 m, lowering the load and reverse driving between position “2” and “3” (distance between 30 m), forward driving from position “3” to “4” (1.5 m distance) followed with lifting load up to 2 m, lowering the load and reverse driving from position “4” to “1.” Tests were carried out at Hot Platinum (Pty) Ltd premises in Athlone, Cape Town, South Africa, Fig. 6.

Developed power pack was able to provide stable operation during VDI60 tests, Fig. 7.

Power pack was tested at ambient temperature of 26.5 °C. energy consumption during VDI60 tests was 9.564 kWh/h compared to 7.5 kWh/h claimed by forklift manufacturer that indicates more aggressive driving (60 cycles in 60 min with 100% load capacity). Peak load power during test was ~35 kW, and fuel cell power was ~14 kW. Even though balance-of-plant components were optimized, BoP power consumption during VDI60 cycle test was still relatively high ~5.1 kWh/h. The main reason for this high BoP consumption is air compressor which requires further air mass flow and pressure optimization. During the tests, MH tank temperature was monitored. It was found that MH tank temperature reaches 50 °C indicating efficient heat transfer between fuel cell coolant and MH tank, Fig. 8.

Fig. 6 Left—shows developed 15 kW—PEMFC power pack before installation in STILL electric forklift. Top right—3-ton concrete blocks used as a load, bottom right—forklift captured during VDI60 driving tests

Fig. 7 Load power, FC power, and BoP power during VDI60 test

Fig. 8 Metal hydride tank and fuel cell stack coolant temperatures during VDI60 tests

4 Conclusion

In this work, development of power pack with original metal hydride hydrogen storage was presented. Power pack was integrated onboard commercial electric forklift from STILL. Before onboard integration, developed system was tested in order to optimize system components. This allows us to use OEM components resulting in system costs reduction. Integration of MH tank allowed to decrease refueling and operating pressures by allowing similar useable hydrogen storage capacity and refueling time compared to the commercial power pack. Developed power pack was tested onboard electric forklift according to VDI60 standard protocol, and it was found that power pack can maintain continuous power during complete 60 VDI test cycles. Moreover, temperatures of fuel cell stack coolant and MH tank were monitored, and it was found that MH tank temperature reaches 50 °C indicating efficient heat transfer from the stack coolant to the MH. Energy consumption was found to be higher than claimed by the forklift manufacturer (9.564 kWh/h vs. 7.5 kWh/h) indicating more aggressive driving. Balance-of-plant consumption during tests was as high as ~5.1 kWh/h mainly due to air compressor. In order to decrease BoP consumption to below 1.5 kWh/h, future compressor optimization is needed.

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